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RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

The importance of this research to Uzbekistan is paramount as the Fifth Industrial Revolution will bring drastic changes in the manufacturing, logistics and service sectors in national scale and may create unforeseen challenges in economic and political landscape of Central Asian countries.

The paper will be made up of four sections, that is, literature review, research method, discussion and conclusion. The research will have a nature of descriptive research as the statement of the problem and data will be profoundly drawn from a body of literature work.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Advanced Engineering Programs in Higher Education in Global Perspectives It is no doubt that behind all technological innovation are advanced engineering programs. But what is generally assumed by the advanced engineering in the context of higher education. Among general characteristics of advanced engineering are its ability to (1) push the boundaries of scientific knowledge, technical skills, and innovative thinking, (2) to solve complex problems and (3) develop technologies across various sub-fields of engineering [3].

The global society has seen the exponential growth of new technological knowledge encompassing the information and communication technologies. Outsourcing and offshoring phenomena have taken the form of new premium of technological workforce. Nevertheless, for the past several years researchers and scholars conclude the urgency to better address the needs of nations in rapidly changing world [4].

Relying only on foreign specialists to solve engineering programs; that is, the outsourcing of engineering services may deteriorate the field of engineering nationwide. In fact, as many US scholars pointed out that outsourcing threaten the erosion of the engineering profession in the United States and hinder the US technological competence and capacity for technological innovation. And for a nation to prosper, it should take the leadership position in technological innovation [5].

The other side of the program is the application and research in the field of engineering, not necessarily confined in one particular nation. Some scholars raise a concern of today's engineering programs, stating that they strive to "educate 21st-century engineers with a 20th-century curriculum delivered in 19th-century institutions" [6].

So, what is the solution? Scholars and professionals in the field of engineering education conclude that the mere reformation of engineering education with old paradigms are not a solution. Rather, it should be transformed into new paradigms to meet the overwhelming challenges in technological and demographic aspects in the global context. [7] Moreover, for a country to prosper, two things must be done: build up a new scientific base through research and take a leading role in advanced technologies [8]. Moreover, for developing countries to grow their own STEM capacities, three major development activities should be implemented; that is, the development of curriculum, facilities, and faculty. And the last will be the most challenging [9].

The Emergence of Fifth Industrial Revolution and its Predecessors

Any business forums today do not stop emphasizing the paramount role of the emergence of the next industrial revolution. But what we really understand by the Fifth Industrial Revolution. The scientific community has come to believe that whatever revolutionary breakthrough we see in the artificial intelligence, in 3D printing, in nanotechnology or Internet of Things, they all will be stepping stones to the Fifth Industrial Revolution [10].

Whatever industrial revolution we have seen today, it all transformed societies. If the invention of steam power was the catalyst for the first industrial revolution, electricity, telecommunication and oil were of the second. How was it reflected on societies? What once was done in manual labor, it was replaced with automated or mechanical work. What once was produced in small workshops, it was then moved in factories. The digital revolution was the third with the boom of the Internet and personal computers. The fourth one was articulated by Klaus Schwab, CEO and founder of the World Economic Forum in 2016. It differs from all its predecessors with the fusion of a number of new technologies in physical, digital and biological dimensions and its ability to interact with a set of systems with speed, depth and breadth [11]. Self-driving cars, drones, robotics, bio-engineering products are fruits of the Fourth Industrial Revolution.

Backbones of Industry 4.0

The Industry 4.0 is all about advanced technologies. It incorporates advanced technologies such as nanotechnology, artificial intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IOT). Nanotechnology is basically about synthesizing nano-materials and controlling their internal structure with arrangement of the atoms and molecules to develop unique products [12]. Artificial intelligence (AI) is taking over many fields of industries. Its ability to simulate human intelligence through obtaining data and using it accordingly produces fast learning machines that are capable to speak, see, understand and reach definite conclusions. Now it is applied in factories, transportation, medical area and more. The Internet of Things (IOT) is when an network of different systems

(computers, mobile phones, etc) interact and exchange information between each other to deliver certain type of tasks whether opening a front door from the distance or turning off devices connected to the wifi networking.

Coming of Fifth Industrial Revolution

Experts believe we may see it on the horizon within ten years. The times span is not that long if we see how long it took its predecessors to come and go. For example, the first industrial revolution lasted about 90 years; the second one, 44; the third, 31. Yes, no doubt that the period between fourth and the fifth revolution will be shorter, but what we really know about the latter and what changes it will bring about we really do not know for sure. Nevertheless, experts believe that a playground of its revolution will be the virtual space, heavily depending data, digital gadgets and the artificial intelligence with the human involvement, merging borders between natural and virtual worlds. Experts are not sure what it will be like, but they are sure it will be far more advanced, efficient, global and intelligent.

RESEARCH METHOD

The research has a nature of descriptive research as the statement of the problem and data have profoundly been drawn from a body of literature work.

DISCUSSION

More Opportunities than Challenges

Back in the mid-18th century when the first industrial revolution broke out in areas such as mining, transportation and agriculture, it was assumed it would create barriers to job opportunities, but against all odds, the reverse was witnessed. Instead, historians write that it brought drastic efficiency in workplaces. The same positive outcome happened with the second revolution (table 1).

The third industrial revolution known as the technological revolution facilitated workload with the invention of cell phones and computers. Just take typewriting grotesque machines as an example. They all were replaced with computers which drastically boosted the communications industries. Or wired phones, which were replaced with cell phones, making a huge shift to digital world.

Table 1. Key Opportunities and Challenges of the Fifth Industrial Revolution.

Aspect	Opportunities	Challenges
Historical Insight	Each past revolution brought efficiency and innovation, not job loss.	Initial fear of job displacement repeated in every industrial revolution.
Technological Impact	Integration of AI, IoT, and robotics improves accuracy and speed.	Workers must adapt to technologies unfamiliar from traditional education.
Human Role	Human-machine collaboration ensures quality control and innovation.	Supervisory and creative roles demand higher-order skills.
Workplace Safety	Machines handle dangerous or exhausting tasks, reducing injury and costs.	Requires reconfiguration of workforce safety training and policies.
Educational Preparedness	Investment in retraining and upskilling becomes essential.	Potential job losses for low-skilled workers if retraining is not addressed.
Economic Efficiency	Reduces operational and insurance costs; enhances productivity.	High initial costs for tech adoption and worker reskilling.

The Internet was the driving force of the fourth industrial revolution. It changed not just how we used to communicate, but also how we came to buy more items online than from traditional stores, make payments or even exchange currencies without going to a local bank, watch media content and more. Now more data is stored, or preserved so to say, in cloud storages around the world that it is on traditional papers. Our cell phones are hundreds times more powerful than computers used during 1960s—an era of the first human step toward the space exploration.

Experts believe that all these have laid out a solid foundation for both emerging the artificial intelligence and merging realm of physical, digital and biological world into one [13].

Human-Machine Collaboration

The fifth industrial revolution is believed to create efficiency, accuracy and speed in manufacturing process through merging advanced technologies: Internet of Things, artificial intelligence and robotics. But it does not mean that we humans will be put aside. Rather, we will supervise the entire manufacturing operation and strive to meet the highest quality standards. Among other things, the safety measures will indeed be taken by

default as dangerous, laborious and traumatic work tasks will be delegated to machines, thus reducing cost of medical bills, sick leaves and insurance claims. At the end of the day, human workers will spend more time on redesigning or refining products to the needs of market demand and focusing on innovation and excellence [14].

Educational Challenges

In the light of idyll, among foreseen challenges are training human workers to operate far-more advanced technologies that they never heard of in their university lecture halls. To help personnel catch up with fruits of industry 5.0, a significant amount of investment would be required and dramatic job displacement will be anticipated among low-skilled workers [15].

CONCLUSION

For the past several years Uzbekistan's new wave of reforms in higher education was reflected with the establishment of dozens of private and international universities across Uzbekistan. In a sense, it drastically improved engineering programs and laid some kind of foundation to meet the Fifth Industrial Revolution. But what challenges this nation can face in the manufacturing, logistics and service sectors in national scale. One particular challenge can be seen in phenomena such outsourcing and offshoring technological workforce. In other words, you let other nations solve your national engineering problems and hence fail to upgrade or even establish your own technological and scientific bases to do the job. The paper concluded that it will not only ruin the national engineering bases, but also pose a threat to a national security. Another concern was that a country should upgrade its old engineering schools to "educate 21st-century engineers" with not of the last century's curriculum or facilities, but with something far more advanced. The solution is simple, but costly. It is of vital importance to nourish Uzbekistan's own STEM capacities, with upgrading curriculum, facilities and faculty.

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